

Noninvasive Profilometry of Sealed Otto Chip Devices by Scanning Optical Reflectometry

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Abstract—Profilometry carried out on a surface having microscale and nanoscale features is an important diagnosis step, in both the electronics and the photonics industry, as well as in research. Nonetheless, few techniques are available for the structural characterization of buried devices. This work evaluates the suitability of an automated reflectometer to perform scanning optical reflectometry (SOR) analysis of quartz sealed plasmonic devices capable of supporting the surface plasmon resonance (SPR) effect in the Otto configuration. The SOR technique was able to fully characterize the devices for quality of sealing between different materials, as well as to map optical parameters of the metallic films and identification of substrate wear, in an automated and noninvasive way. Devices with 9 and 1.4 cm² of area are characterized, and the minimum gap between layers measured was 0.69 μm. A defective device was also identified through SOR and its defects were confirmed by reflectance microscopy.

Index Terms—Characterization, optical reflectometry, profilometry, sealed devices, surface plasmon resonance (SPR).

I. INTRODUCTION

SCANNING techniques for profilometry of devices and structures are important tools both in the electronics and in the photonics industries, as well as in research. To acquire the profile of a particular structure, two main types of equipment are employed, namely, contact and noncontact profilometers. One example of a contact-type device is the traditional stylus profilometer [1], which can measure roughness, waviness, and step heights across a substrate, with lateral resolution smaller than 0.5 nm and vertical resolution of 10 nm. This

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technique can also be used to obtain a profile of curved surfaces [2]. Aspheric surfaces can have its profile measured by swing arm profilometry, in which a rotation stage is employed to permit translation of the probe in a curved trajectory [3], [4]. The atomic force microscope (AFM) [5] and the scanning tunneling microscope (STM) [6], [7], which is a pseudo-contact procedure, have much better lateral and height resolutions relative to direct contact approaches, with the AFM being capable to map atom size features across a surface. On the other hand, noncontact techniques include coherence scanning interferometry (CSI) [8] and its associated variations [9], confocal microscopy [10] including fiber based instruments [11], focus variation techniques [12], and digital holography microscopy [13], [14], observing that the latter is not a scanning technique. Three-dimensional techniques such as fringe projection profilometry are useful for macroscopic object profile measurement with low-cost systems [15], [16], and phase shift algorithms can be employed to minimize error [17], [18]. All the procedures cited above are limited when it comes to buried devices. To measure the profile of such a structure, a laser-based reflectance interrogation method can be more suited since it can carry information about an entire multilayer configuration depending on the thickness of each layer.

Considering reflectometer equipment and experimental implementations, different approaches have been used for a number of applications, such as the previously mentioned stylus profilometer [1] and beam profile reflectometry [19]. Optical properties of TiO₂ were measured in an angle-interrogated reflectometry experimental setup with 2° to 82° angular range and 130–226-nm spectral range, with results compared to ellipsometry obtained data [20]. In such work, the optical constants of the film were obtained by conducting a regression analysis over the experimental data. A number of implementations of angle-resolved measurements were developed, that permit, depending on the electromechanical apparatus, obtaining high resolution and automation of the process, for example, the employment of digital light processing (DLP) projector for generation of ring patterned fringes with direct association with the angle of incidence with possibility of angle-resolved spectral measurement with angular uncertainty in the order of 0.1° [21]. In the case of weakly absorbing films, a multiple linear regression strategy over phase signal from an angle-resolved reflectometry in order to mitigate correlation between the measured parameters was proposed

with an angular uncertainty of 0.2° [22]. Setups were also proposed considering a broadband light source and analysis of the state of polarization of the reflected beam in association with imaging spectroscopy, so the thickness and refractive index can be fit in both angular and spectral domains, leading to real-time measurement in the context of ultrathin-film characterization [23]. A strategy of fitting momentum resolved data obtained from angle-resolved measurements was also proposed to avoid dealing with models with too many free parameters in ellipsometry techniques [24]. Interferometric analysis based on transmittance of plane parallel structures was suggested for precise wavelength measurements [25], and such mathematical analysis was employed together with high refractive index materials for film thickness measurement based on the separation between fringes, also in an angle-resolved experimental setup [26]. Interference-based transmittance analysis was also proposed with an angle-resolved experimental setup in order to measure refractive index and film thickness from a phase measurement with incidence in two different wavelengths as a strategy of dealing with 2π ambiguity [27]. These techniques did not address the quality of adhesion between different layers of a particular structure or device. According to the author's knowledge, there is no suggestion for optical reflectometry applied to profilometry and characterization of surfaces in sealed devices except for the preliminary investigation reported in [28], [29], and [30].

The problem of acquiring the profile of a buried structure emerges from the need of a characterization method for plasmonic devices such as the Otto chip [31]. Unlike the Kretschmann configuration [32], Otto devices have a small dielectric gap, usually comprising a gas or liquid medium, in sensing applications, between the input medium, which is a prism, and the metallic film. This structure has been historically avoided in the construction of practical plasmonic sensing devices, and to the best of the author's knowledge, only one device, alongside its different versions, based on this configuration was fabricated [30], [31], [33]. A scanning optical reflectometry (SOR) approach along with proper analytical tools, as developed in the present work, can be suitable for mapping the regions of interest in a particular device, in turn providing a method that can be fully automated and applicable for large-scale characterization of Otto chip devices or other similar cavity buried structures. The SOR method scans the chip area yielding angle-resolved reflectance curves for multiple points on the surface of the sample device and allows mapping the sample topography. This work implements the technique with the use of an automated reflectometer and associated model functions and nonlinear regression methods. The SOR procedure is performed for three different sample devices.

II. SOR AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

The SOR technique consists in measuring several angle or wavelength spectra of the reflectance function of a particular device. In this work, the technique is implemented by measuring the angle spectra of the reflectance function for a fixed wavelength. This approach with proper modeling and associated regression algorithm enables determining the

Fig. 1. Automated reflectometer and experimental setup. PD and SM refer to photodetector and stepper motor, respectively. The inset image shows the normalized beam intensity spatial profile in red and a Gaussian fit in blue, versus radial distance in millimeters.

structure profile in a noninvasive manner. This technique aims to solve the problem of characterization of plasmonic devices such as the Otto chip structure [34] with the possibility of complete automation of the process. To evaluate the degree of characterization capability of the technique, an angle-resolved automated reflectometer is employed to conduct SOR experiments in three different versions of the Otto chip [31], [33], [35].

A. Automated Reflectometer

The automated reflectometer and overall experimental setup are shown in Fig. 1. The system employs an infrared single-mode diode laser manufactured by Melles Griot as a light source operating at a wavelength of 975.1 nm, with 0.14 mrad of beam divergence and 73 mW of emitting power. The laser beam divergence and spatial profile were obtained by measuring the beam waist using a charge-coupled device (CCD) in two different positions along propagation. The inset image in Fig. 1 shows in red the experimentally obtained normalized beam intensity profile versus radial distance in millimeters and in blue the Gaussian curve fit, with $R^2 = 0.99727$. The laser beam has a 1.07 mm diameter after being collimated by a lens—not shown in the picture—and is partially transmitted through a 1-mm-diameter iris. The polarizer guarantees that the incident light on the device is p -polarized so as to enable observing surface plasmon resonance (SPR) effect in the metallized portions of the device. The beam splitter reflects half of the optical power to the photodetector PD_R allowing

elimination of intensity fluctuations. The BK7 prism position and angle are controlled by the control and acquisition system, which employs an association of three stepper motors. As illustrated in Fig. 1, motors SM_x and SM_y actuate on two orthogonal directions along the upper surface of the prism and SM_θ controls the rotation stage enabling an angle-resolved measurement. Since there is an angular offset considering the possible loosening of the rotational stage, both clockwise and anti-clockwise angular offsets were measured by conducting reflectometer analysis for the prism–air interface alone in nine different points and fitting the offset parameters in comparison with the Brewster angle. This offset is compensated in every measurement conducted with sample devices. The maximum angular error expected from this setup is $\pm 0.008^\circ$. The SM_w motor is set to search for the maximum optical signal on the photodetector PD_S during the experiment in order to guarantee that the detector is always aligned with the output laser beam.

The incident beam on the sample device surface has, at 45° of incidence, an elliptical footprint with major axes of 1 and 1.4 mm, the latter dimension parallel to the plane of incidence. This estimation is obtained by covering the left surface of the prism with a photosensitive card and measuring the size of the footprint. Then, one can calculate the expected footprint on the top surface. The reflectometer can be programmed by a set of simple commands in order to perform a full device profilometry, and for this, the user provides the system values for surface range, angular resolution, angular range, and spacing between measurement points. The reflectance is calculated by the normalized ratio of the intensities measured by PD_S and PD_R , with each point being averaged from 100 measurements. The mentioned ratio was measured over the course of 30 h to measure fluctuations associated with the laser and harmonics of the power supply. In such measurement reflectance peaks of ± 0.001 , a 0.0005 noise and signal drift of 0.002 are identified. Considering this, it is used as the maximum error in reflectance, the value of ± 0.002 . Both PD_S and PD_R are Si p-i-n photodiodes DET100 manufactured by Thorlabs.

The control and acquisition system pictured in Fig. 1 performs a linear adjustment in the x axis in order to maintain a stationary laser footprint during an angular scan [36]. This control procedure guarantees that the entire angular scan occurs on a single spot on the superior prism surface with a resolution of $5 \mu\text{m}$. This resolution is to be compared with the estimated laser footprint over the surface of 1.4×1 mm, thus yielding a very accurate measurement.

B. Otto Chip Devices

The Otto chip is fabricated according to the process described in [31]. All the configurations are devices with a sealing quartz window. Within the device, there is an air gap between the bottom of the quartz window and the exposed metal surface. For chips #1 and #2, this gap is approximately $2.2 \mu\text{m}$. For chip #3, there are distinct gaps within the chip, from 1.8 to $3.3 \mu\text{m}$ in steps of $0.5 \mu\text{m}$, as illustrated in Fig. 2. A fabrication parametric study was performed to achieve the mentioned gap dimensions.

Fig. 2. Otto chip device structures and dimensions. (a) Device #1 and designed values for air gap and film thickness. (b) Device #2, without inlet/outlet channels. (c) Device #3, multigap structure and designed values for each gap and film thickness.

Fig. 3. Otto chip device dimensions. (a) Chips #1 and #2, with the exception of the device #2 that does not have the circular inlet/outlet pair. (b) Chip #3.

Fig. 3 shows the dimensions for each version. Considering the dimensions for each device, two experimental protocols were prepared, one for the multigap chip and another for the remaining devices. Both protocols were conducted with 0.014° of angular resolution and range of incident angles from 40° to 45° . For the single gap devices, the experimental protocol comprised a single scan of the chip area on a square grid

Fig. 4. SOR experimental protocols. (a) Single scan for devices #1 and #2, grid spacing of 2 mm. (b) Dual scan for device #3. Black dots represent a grid with 1-mm spacing and red dots are on a grid with a 1.5-mm spacing.

of 2 mm, as illustrated in Fig. 4(a). For the multigap device, a double scan protocol was employed, using two distinct grids on the chip area, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). By use of one coarse and one fine grid, in a double scan scheme with 1.5- and 1-mm spacing, it was possible to map the entire chip area with improved resolution, relative to that obtained by a single scan scheme. The double scan scheme was used on a 20×20 mm area of the chip, which contained the relevant features of the active area, as illustrated in Fig. 4(b). This protocol was employed considering it provided a reasonable resolution for interpolation in order to build color maps for identifying regions of interest. Another reason for this choice is the assumption that possible bubbles caused by lack of proper adhesion between layers would not suffer from drastic variations. If a particular zone of the device needs to be inspected, a finer grid can be employed to obtain measurement points concentrated in such area.

III. RESULTS AND DATA ANALYSIS

A. Plane Wave Model and Qualitative Analysis

In this section, one presents the measured results along with the theoretical modeling to extract information from the SOR data. SOR analysis of chip #1 is shown in Fig. 5. Measured data are initially modeled by either single or double interface Fresnel coefficients. Further consideration on model functions

Fig. 5. Experimental curves and rough model estimates associated with the laser footprint location on the chip. (a) Labels of the laser footprint on the chip corresponding to each set of curves. (b)–(g) Corresponding model and experimental curves. The type of model function and parameter values are indicated in each plot. Optical constants used in the simulations are listed in Table I. Data obtained from chip #1.

is given in Section III-B. For a double interface structure, the angle-dependent reflectance can be written in the form [37]

$$R_d(\theta) = \left| \frac{r_1 + r_2 \exp(-j2k_2d)}{1 + r_1r_2 \exp(-j2k_2d)} \right|^2 \quad (1)$$

where d is the gap thickness

$$r_i = \frac{\epsilon_i k_{i+1} - \epsilon_{i+1} k_i}{\epsilon_i k_{i+1} + \epsilon_{i+1} k_i} \quad (2)$$

is the single interface reflection coefficient associated with the i th interface, with $i = 1, 2$ and

$$k_i = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} (\epsilon_i - \epsilon_1 \sin^2\theta)^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

TABLE I
OPTICAL CONSTANTS FOR SI, BK7, AND AU USED IN THE
SIMULATIONS, AT $\lambda = 975.1$ NM [38], [39], [40]

Material	n	κ
Si	3.5882	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-3}$
BK7	1.5079	$9.8525 \cdot 10^{-9}$
Au	0.21516	6.2835

with λ representing the wavelength and ϵ_i the relative permittivity of medium i , with $i = 1, 2, 3$. The single interface reflectance is given by

$$R_s(\theta) = |r_i|^2. \quad (4)$$

From the SOR experiments, it was possible to identify a few patterns in the obtained reflectance curves. Each pattern was then associated with a specific zone of the device. These included the active region, defined here as the area of the gold film where SPR was observed with significant coupling; areas of nonuniform sealing between quartz and Si; and regions of worn substrate and interfaces between two different materials or structures. In Fig. 5, experimental curves are shown together with the theoretical model represented by either R_d or R_s , given by (1) and (4), respectively, for the designed structure and parameters. Optical constants for Si were obtained from an interpolation of data from [38], and for BK7, Sellmeier's coefficients obtained from [39] were employed, as listed in Table I. Optical constants of Au were obtained from [40]. This preliminary comparison allows a qualitative identification of the distinct regions of the device.

Fig. 5(b). shows the case for a curve obtained in the Au film where theory and experiment are in agreement, considering the designed parameters. This type of behavior is modeled by a nonlinear regression algorithm discussed in Section III-C. Fig. 5(c) shows an example curve obtained in the Si cavity and some mismatching is observed in this case, indicating an air gap value different than the designed one. The measured curve of Fig. 5(d) shows an example of ideal sealing between quartz and Si, as modeled by (4). A particular pattern is observed in areas where, ideally, the optical response should be similar to a quartz/Si interface, but the experimental data show signs of interference. Such curves are interpreted as obtained at a point where the sealing between the two materials is nonuniform, and in such points, there is a nonuniform air layer between quartz and Si, which means that the structure rather than be modeled by the single interface function (4) should be represented by the double interface function (1), corresponding to a quartz/air/Si configuration. Fig. 5(e) shows an example of such behavior alongside the model function (1). Some curves were measured on the inlet/outlet of the cavity, as shown in Fig. 5(f), locations where the curves are well fit by model (4) for a quartz/air interface. One last pattern is found, corresponding to curves obtained between two different structures, in this case, quartz/air/Si and quartz/air/Au.

One can notice deviations of the model function (1) relative to the data for the cases of Fig. 5(e) and (g). For the case of Fig. 5(g), the laser footprint is sitting on the edge between bare metal and its Si-air-quartz region of the chip. In Fig 5(e), a certain degree of interference appears to take place,

probably due to a nonuniform air layer in a region supposed to be a single quartz-Si interface. Additional effects may occur if the beam divergence is taken into account. All these possible effects are addressed in Section III-B.

B. Modified Model Functions

Two important effects may influence the overall reflectance function across different portions of the measured chips. One is that due to a small, but not negligible, beam divergence of the laser. The diode laser used in the reflectometer has an estimated beam divergence of approximately 0.14 mrad or, equivalently, 0.008°. The interfering patterns in the reflectance wave shape occur in an angular range that can be as small as 0.05°. Thus, the laser beam divergence has some broadening effect in the overall reflectance wave shape. To take the effect of beam divergence into account, by use of a Gaussian beam model [41], [42], one assumes the beam power density having a profile of the form

$$g(\Delta\theta) = A \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta\theta^2}{\theta_{1/2}^2}\right) \quad (5)$$

where $\theta_{1/2}$ represents the half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) of the beam divergence and A is a normalization constant. In (5), $\Delta\theta$ is the angle variation across the beam, relative to the incidence angle. In practice, the normalization constant A can be determined by imposing

$$\int_{-W}^W g(x) dx = 1 \quad (6)$$

with $W \gg \theta_{1/2}$. By using a reasonable value of W , e.g., $W \approx 10\theta_{1/2}$, integration in (6) becomes invariant with W . Thus, one can use, e.g.,

$$\int_{-10\theta_{1/2}}^{10\theta_{1/2}} g(x) dx = 1. \quad (7)$$

The numerical calculation of (7) yields $A \approx 4/(5\theta_{1/2})$, and thus, a suitable beam divergence function is of the form

$$g(\Delta\theta) = \frac{4}{5\theta_{1/2}} \exp\left(-\frac{2\Delta\theta^2}{\theta_{1/2}^2}\right). \quad (8)$$

By use of the Gaussian beam model function $g(\Delta\theta)$, the reflectance function R_{gb} , taking into account the beam divergence, can be determined by use of the convolution-type integral

$$R_{gb} = \frac{4}{5\theta_{1/2}} \int_{\theta-10\theta_{1/2}}^{\theta+10\theta_{1/2}} R(\theta') \exp\left[-\frac{2(\theta' - \theta)^2}{\theta_{1/2}^2}\right] d\theta' \quad (9)$$

where θ represents the outer incidence angle at the input beam and R represents the reflectance in the plane wave approximation, as given by (1).

A second consideration, based on direct experimental observation, is the need to take into account situations where the footprint is located on an edge between distinct materials on the surface. In this case, the intensity distribution in the far-field will have a term that is a linear combination of intensities and an interference term due to the sudden height variation

at the edge. This interference term, when integrated across the photodetector active area, yields a negligible contribution. Thus, to take into account edge effects, one assumes a model function in the form of the linear combination

$$R'(\rho, \theta) \equiv \rho R_{\text{gb1}}(\theta) + (1 - \rho) R_{\text{gb2}}(\theta) \quad (10)$$

with $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$, representing a fraction of the beam footprint on region 1 of the surface, with its remaining fraction $(1 - \rho)$ incident on region 2. In (10), R_{gb1} and R_{gb2} are the modified reflectance functions calculated from (9) for regions 1 and 2, respectively.

C. Nonlinear Regression From SPR Data

One particular region of the Otto chip that demands a specific method of data analysis is the active region, in which a nonlinear regression algorithm applied to a given resonance curve returns two different solution sets of three parameters [37]. Each set comprises the real and imaginary parts of the complex refractive index and the gap thickness [31], [43]. There are two goals to be attained, namely obtaining the best out of two solutions and obtaining them in an automated systematic way. For doing so, an algorithm implementing initial estimates for the fit parameters followed by nonlinear regression was developed, based on the reports of [35] and [43] and the algorithm described in [44].

The algorithm analyzes each resonance curve individually and calculates the minimum reflectance (R_{min}), the resonance angle (θ_{rps}), and the HWHM (W_{sp}) from experimental data. By modeling the resonance using an Lorentzian approximation and employing the experimental parameters previously calculated, an initial estimate for the initial guess vector $\vec{v} \equiv (\{n_1, n_2\}, \{k_1, k_2\}, \{d_1, d_2\})$ is obtained for both solutions, as outlined in the Appendix. This approximation is not sufficient for providing initial guesses good enough to systematically obtain both solutions for the curve, so the vector calculated from the Lorentzian approximation is then enhanced by numerically solving a set of nonlinear equations, as outlined in [44]. Algorithm 1 summarizes the nonlinear regression procedure and overall experimental data analysis routine.

IV. QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF MEASURED DATA

A. Selected Examples of Data Modeling

With the new formalism of (9) and (10) alongside the analysis algorithm exposed in Algorithm 1, curves in the metallic, nonuniform, and edge regions are quantitatively analyzed. Fig. 6(a) shows an example of both obtained solutions for a typical SPR curve. In this case, the solution chosen to be the correct one is the one that shows the smallest root-mean-square error, which is the solution defined by the optical constants $n = 0.23$, $\kappa = 6.07$, and gap thickness $d = 1.85 \mu\text{m}$. Considering that the thickness of 300 nm of the metal film would result in properties more similar to the bulk material, the values for n and κ are compared and checked to be in accordance with the data in [40], with 5.5% of deviation for refractive index and 3.4% for extinction coefficient. The gap thickness obtained by regression is compared to the design value of $2.2 \mu\text{m}$, within 15.7%. To highlight the effect of the

Algorithm 1 Pseudocode for Overall Analysis Routine

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input Set of experimental curves of a particular device;  $n \leftarrow$ 
  Number of experimental curves to be analyzed;
   $i \leftarrow 0$ ;
  while  $i \neq n$  do
    Reads file number  $i$ ;
    if Interference is detected then
      Apply model (9) to experimental data with a
      quartz/air/Si structure and  $\theta_{1/2} = 0.3$  mrad;
      Apply initial guess for air gap thickness  $d_0 = 2.2 \mu\text{m}$ ;
      Air layer thickness  $d$  is obtained by regression;
      Returns fit air gap thickness  $d$  value;
    end if
    if Edge region is detected then
      Apply model (10) to experimental data for  $R_{\text{gb1}}$  with
      a quartz/air/Au structure and  $R_{\text{gb2}}$  with a quartz/air/Si
      structure;
      Apply initial guess  $\rho = 0$ ;
       $\rho$  parameter is obtained by regression;
      Returns fit  $\rho$  parameter;
    end if
    if Resonance is detected then
      Calculates  $R_{\text{min}}$ ,  $\theta_{\text{rps}}$  and half-width-at-half-maximum
       $W_{\text{sp}}$  from experimental data;
       $\vec{v} \leftarrow$  Eq.(A15), (A16) and (A17);
       $\vec{v} \leftarrow$  Enhanced solutions according to [44];
      Performs nonlinear regression and obtain two solution
      curves, one for each enhanced initial guess from vector
       $\vec{v}$ ;
      Calculates rms (Root Mean Square) error for both
      curves respective to experimental data;
      Returns solution with lower error;
    end if
     $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
  end while
  Generate plots;

```

three variables, Fig. 6(b) shows the sensitivity of the curve for a 15% variation on each parameter. The comparison is conducted considering the previously chosen solution.

Fig 7 shows the curves obtained in the nonuniform sealing region alongside model (9) for a quartz/air/Si interface with air layer thickness of $11.25 \mu\text{m}$, obtained from regression, and three different values for $\theta_{1/2}$ to qualitatively analyze the broadening effect in such cases. It is important to mention that the angular variation, even if it is small, has an influence on the size of the laser footprint on the surface of the device, producing a lack of accordance between the theory and experiment at lower angles. There is also the possibility of a focusing behavior since the quartz/air interface is not exactly planar throughout the nonuniformity zone. Nonetheless, it is possible to clearly identify the valleys of the interference pattern and obtain a good estimate of the air layer thickness since $\theta_{1/2}$ and gap thickness are uncorrelated variables. It is also important to mention that the uncertainty of our method is smaller compared to previous works that provide accurate measurements of film thickness [21], [22], reaffirming that our

Fig. 6. (a) Experimental resonance curve with both solutions, according to model (1). Curve in accordance with Fig. 5(b). (b) Sensitivity of resonance curve to each parameter.

Fig. 7. Experimental curve in the nonuniform sealing area and theory for plane wave and Gaussian beam in a quartz/air/Si structure according to model (1) and (9), respectively. Curve in accordance with Fig. 5(e).

result is reliable. It is also important to mention that the fitting analysis based directly on fringe separation presented in [26] could be employed with SOR as well.

Fig. 8. Experimental curve between the quartz/air/Si and quartz/air/Au structures and theory for $\rho = 0.77, 1$, and 0 , according to model (10). Curve in accordance with Fig. 5(g).

TABLE II
MISALIGNMENT RESULTS FOR EACH DEVICE

Device	δ_x (mm)	δ_y (mm)	δ_ϕ (mm)
Chip #1	3	2.5	0
Chip #2	0	3	0
Chip #3	0	0	0

Fig. 8 shows an experimental curve obtained on the edge of the metallic film alongside model (10) for R_{gb1} representing the reflectance for quartz/air/Au structure, with the designed value of $2.2 \mu\text{m}$ for the air gap, and R_{gb2} the one for the quartz/air/Si structure for the designed value of $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ for the air layer. In this case, a regression for the parameter ρ was conducted with 0 being the initial guess since $0 \leq \rho \leq 1$.

B. Device Profilometry

With the reanalyzed curves, one can start mapping all the zones of interest of the device, but the limits of each area could be uncertain in the cases of mispositioned samples over the prism surface. To calculate and correct the position on the device area where each curve was measured, a virtual chip aligner algorithm was developed. This algorithm permits choosing a particular point on the measurement spots grid while showing the location of such point on the surface of the device and allows the virtual displacement of the chip. By visually identifying particular patterns on the curves such as edge of the metallic film, the end of the Si cavity or curves obtained on the inlet/outlet of the channel, one can estimate, by a manual adjustment, the 2-D displacement of the device to the original matrix of measured points. The angular tilt of the chip, relative to the prism surface coordinates, is also estimated. Fig. 9 shows the representation of each dimension being estimated by this procedure and the results for each device are shown in Table II.

1) *Device #1*: With the correction of the position and the theoretical treatment elapsed in this section being applied to each obtained curve, one can now create maps of the surface

Fig. 9. Scheme representing a misaligned sample device and the obtained values for each chip.

Fig. 10. Nonuniformity area A for chip #1 and wore substrate area B.

of the device in terms of the gap between quartz and Si in a nonuniform sealing area. This allows the identification, for each device, the total area where the sealing is not ideal with precision related to the spacing of the measured points grid. From the maps shown in Fig. 10, we can infer the overall quality of the sealing of the investigated device. This information is important for classifying the mechanical stability of the chip and also shows that the SOR technique can be used to study the quality of adhesion between different materials. In some measured curves in the Si cavity in which the obtained gap thickness showed a deviation greater than 15% of the designed value were considered points of the Si surface where the substrate has suffered some kind of wear. The areas of worn substrate were also identified in chip #1 in Fig 10.

Device #1 shows a reasonably small area of worn substrate with a maximum 6.8- μm air layer thickness and a nonuniform sealing area that does not impose a mechanical instability of the chip with a maximum air layer thickness of 11.3 μm .

The active region of the device was also evaluated. Fig. 11 shows for device #1, the collection of all curves that exhibited a resonance behavior alongside a color map for gap thickness obtained from the regression. The color maps are a third-order interpolation of the values associated with their location on the grid of measured spots, which translates to the position on the device surface. Twenty SPR curves were obtained in

Fig. 11. (a) Collection of SPR curves and (b) gap thickness color map for chip #1.

Fig. 12. Nonuniformity area A for chip #2 and wore substrate area B.

this chip, with a minimum and maximum obtained gap of 1.65 and 2.2 μm , respectively.

2) *Device #2*: Device #2 underwent the same procedure of device #1. Fig. 12 shows both color maps for nonuniform sealing and wore substrate areas. In this particular chip, both areas were found to be more extensive in comparison with device #1; nonetheless, mechanical instability was not observed in this chip. Maximum air layer thicknesses obtained for nonuniform and wore substrate areas were 22.6 and 15.1 μm , respectively.

Sixteen SPR curves were obtained in this chip, as shown in Fig 13(a), alongside gap thickness mapping in Fig. 13(b).

Fig. 13. (a) Collection of SPR curves and (b) gap thickness color map for chip #2.

Minimum and maximum gap thicknesses obtained from regression were 1.32 and 0.69 μm , respectively.

3) *Device #3*: underwent similar procedures as devices #1 and #2. However, only two cases of curves indicating nonuniformity were observed for the chip #3, and considering that the maps are formed by a third-order interpolation, it was not possible to create a trustworthy representation of the zone with such few data. From such a small area where sealing was not ideal, we can conclude that chip #3 was mechanically stable.

The results obtained from the SOR analysis for the chip #3 showed poor performance for this particular device and only seven of the obtained curves showed a slight resonant behavior. Considering this, results from SOR for chip #3 are shown in Fig. 14, but no color map of the active region of this device was created. It is also important to notice that the optical constants obtained in the regression show a greater deviation from the literature values than the previous devices, as well as unexpected behavior beyond the total internal reflection angle. Because of the low number of measurements where the SPR effect was actually observed and the previous considerations about film characterization, this device was visually inspected by reflected light microscopy and compared to the standard chip #1, chosen because of the larger area active region. Fig. 15 shows the difference between the quality of the Au film in both devices.

In addition to poor results from SOR, the optical microscopy indicates that the Au film in chip #3 is damaged. From Fig. 15(a), the first diagnostic was that the electron beam evaporation process was conducted with less material than expected to actually deposit the 200-nm film, consisting in the

Fig. 14. Active region mapping. (a) Collection of curves in which SPR phenomena are observed. (b) Example of experimental curve alongside regression results using model (1).

Fig. 15. Reflected light microscopy analysis. (a) Multigap chip (#4) metallic film image. (b) Standard (#1) chip metallic film.

hypothesis that the figure shows a structure that the deposition process was interrupted.

On a device quality inspection perspective, sealing nonuniformity data could be explored as a reliability metric, considering that a nonideal sealing zone from the chip outer limits ranging to the Si cavity could lead to device contamination in practical operation of the sensor.

The results presented in this section show that a plasmonic device based on the Otto configuration can be characterized by the SOR technique and this procedure can be applied to future SPR-based integrated devices. It can also be noted that there are some aspects of the technique that make it a suitable

candidate for the characterization of different structures where it is important to measure the quality of adhesion between two different layers. The profilometry performed here can also characterize gaps in Si cavities and measure the quality of the substrate itself, which can be useful for Si-based structures such as micro-electromechanical systems or silicon photonics devices. The technique reported in this work also permits the possibility of a fully automated process for multiple device characterization.

V. CONCLUSION

It is evident from the results and subsequent discussion that the SOR technique is well-suited for the automatic characterization of surfaces and can be effectively employed in the profilometry of sealed devices, such as the Otto chip. The automation of this technique is achieved through mechanical hardware and an associated electronic control and acquisition system, with sample positioning being the only nonautomated step. The technique presented in this work enables the mapping of the entire chip surface and the identification of zones of interest, such as the active region of the device, wear of the Si substrate, nonuniform sealing, and interfaces between different materials. This capability allows for the measurement of metallic film quality and adhesion between materials following the deposition or growth of the upper layer, as well as an investigation of the effects of the final fabrication step and buried structures. This represents a significant advancement, as it enables the inspection of internal layers in devices after fabrication is completed and even after they have been used or operated.

The problem of obtaining both solutions for the characterization of the optical constants of the metal is addressed through the Lorentzian approximation of the curve and enhanced initial guesses. This approach allows for the automatic determination of the two solutions that best fit the experimental data by performing regression analysis on a set of curves and subsequent choice of the correct one based on minimum error criteria. The characterization of air gaps between materials, which are directly related to interlayer adhesion, is conducted by regressing the thickness parameter against an interference model, as the number of fringes is correlated with layer thickness. These features of the technique demonstrate that SOR is a promising candidate for the characterization of future integrated plasmonic devices, including in mass production scenarios.

The hardware used in the construction of the automated reflectometer demonstrates that the equipment can be replicated using commercial components. Furthermore, SOR can be applied to the simultaneous characterization of multiple devices, indicating its compatibility with high-volume production. Additional applications of SOR may include the mapping of surface magnetization via the magneto-optical Kerr effect, provided that both polarizations are measured separately.

Future work will involve a more rigorous analysis of regression procedures for SPR curves, with a focus on investigating the role of beam divergence on the obtained optical parameters and the adoption of different fitting strategies such as the fringe spacing technique for thickness measurement that

could potentially lead to more accurate determination of the nonuniform sealing layers. The characterization of Pd-based plasmonic devices for hydrogen (H₂) sensing is also of interest to the research group.

APPENDIX

INITIAL GUESSES ESTIMATIONS BY LORENTZIAN APPROXIMATION

For the SPR data, the objective is to determine the gap thickness d and the real and imaginary parts of the metal complex permittivity

$$\epsilon_3 \equiv \epsilon' - j\epsilon'' \quad (\text{A1})$$

with $\epsilon' < 0$ and $\epsilon'' > 0$.

To obtain two sets of initial guesses to be used in the nonlinear regression algorithm, one approximates the measured reflectance, in the resonance region by the Lorentzian form [45]

$$R = 1 - \frac{(1 - R_{\min}) W_{\text{sp}}^2}{(\theta - \theta_{\text{sp}})^2 + W_{\text{sp}}^2}. \quad (\text{A2})$$

By the use of the measured reflectance and the approximate model (A2), one obtains the resonance angle θ_{sp} , the HWHM W_{sp} , and the minimum reflectance R_{\min} . In terms of the surface plasmon (SP) propagation factor, the Lorentzian approximation is of the form [37]

$$R = 1 - \frac{4k_{\text{sgl}}'' k_{\text{rad}}''}{(k_x - k_{\text{sp}}')^2 + k_{\text{sgl}}''^2} \quad (\text{A3})$$

with

$$k_{\text{sp}} \equiv k_{\text{sgl}} + k_{\text{rad}} \equiv k_{\text{sp}}' - jk_{\text{sp}}'' \quad (\text{A4})$$

representing the SP complex propagation factor, with

$$k_{\text{sgl}} \equiv k_{\text{sgl}}' - jk_{\text{sgl}}'' \quad (\text{A5})$$

representing the complex component that would be obtained assuming a single air-metal interface, and

$$k_{\text{rad}} \equiv k_{\text{rad}}' - jk_{\text{rad}}'' \quad (\text{A6})$$

the additional component, taking into account the finite gap distance between the input glass window and the metal surface, in turn accounts for radiation effects on the SP propagation. In (A5) and (A6), the propagation factors are written so that the parameters on the RHS of the expressions are positively defined. Expressions for the relevant parameters in (A5) and (A6) can be written in the forms [34]

$$k_{\text{sgl}}' = k_0 \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon'}{\epsilon' + 1}} \quad (\text{A7})$$

$$k_{\text{sgl}}'' = k_{\text{sgl}}' \frac{\epsilon''}{2\epsilon'(\epsilon' + 1)} \quad (\text{A8})$$

and

$$k_{\text{rad}}'' = \frac{4(\epsilon' \gamma k_{10} n)^2}{(\epsilon'^2 - 1)(n^4 \gamma^2 + k_{10}^2)} k_{\text{sgl}}' \exp(-2\gamma d) \quad (\text{A9})$$

with

$$\gamma = \frac{k_0}{\sqrt{|\epsilon' + 1|}} \quad (\text{A10})$$

$$k_{10} = k_0 \sqrt{n^2 - \frac{\epsilon'}{\epsilon' + 1}} \quad (\text{A11})$$

and

$$k_0 \equiv \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}. \quad (\text{A12})$$

The degree of coupling of the input beam with an SP is determined by the coupling coefficient

$$\eta \equiv \frac{k''_{\text{sgl}}}{k''_{\text{rad}}} \quad (\text{A13})$$

which can be obtained from (A3) in the resonance condition

$$\eta_{\pm} = \frac{1}{1 - R_{\min}} \left(1 + R_{\min} \pm 2 \sqrt{R_{\min}} \right). \quad (\text{A14})$$

Thus, by approximating the SPR curve by a Lorentzian wave shape, two sets of values for ϵ' , ϵ'' , and d are obtained. The relationships between material parameters and experimental parameters obtained from [45] can be cast in the form

$$\epsilon' = -\frac{n^2 \sin^2 \theta_{\text{sp}}}{n^2 \sin^2 \theta_{\text{sp}} - 1} \quad (\text{A15})$$

$$\epsilon'' = \frac{\eta}{\eta + 1} 2\epsilon' (\epsilon' + 1) \cotan \theta_{\text{sp}} W_{\text{sp}} \quad (\text{A16})$$

$$d = \frac{1}{2\gamma} \text{Ln}f \quad (\text{A17})$$

with

$$f \equiv \eta \frac{4(\epsilon' \gamma k_{10} n)^2}{(\epsilon' - 1)(n^4 \gamma^2 + k_{10}^2) k''_{\text{sgl}} k''_{\text{rad}}} \quad (\text{A18})$$

and $n^2 = \epsilon_1$.

These are used as initial guesses and are subjected to the enhancement algorithm that aprimorates the solution by solving a set of nonlinear equations. Only then, the final values are input in the nonlinear regression algorithm. One then selects the set of parameters \vec{v} that yields the smallest rms error relative to the experimental curve.

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